

Article

Culture and production of *Lucilia sericata* Meigen (1826) larvae for rearing stinging catfish *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch, 1794) using poultry waste

Abdus Satter^{1*}, Md. Ahsan Bin Habib², Hadi Hamli³, Abdulla-Al-Asif³ and Jamil⁴

¹Department of Fisheries, Bangamata Sheikh Fojilatunnesa Mujib Science and Technology University, Melandah, Jamalpur, Bangladesh

²Department of Aquaculture, Faculty of Fisheries, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh-2202, Bangladesh

³Department of Animal Science and Fishery, Faculty of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Bintulu Sarawak Campus, Jalan Nyabau 97008, Bintulu, Sarawak, Malaysia

⁴Department of Fisheries Management, Faculty of Fisheries, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, 2202, Bangladesh

*Corresponding author: Abdus Satter, Department of Fisheries, Bangamata Sheikh Fojilatunnesa Mujib Science and Technology University, Melandah, Jamalpur, Bangladesh. Email: satter@bsfmstu.ac.bd

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Abstract: The fly larvae (*Lucilia sericata*) are being used as an alternative protein source in any kind of animal feed as it reduces the cost of preparation of feed. This current study focused on the physico-chemical and proximate properties of raw poultry waste, while this study also revealed the production process of fly larvae and the proximate composition of it. The poultry waste was collected from Suvro poultry farm, Sutiakhali, Mymensingh, then the physico-chemical properties of the raw poultry waste were determined using different procedures. Three treatments were considered for production of fly larvae, T₁ (3 kg), T₂ (6 kg) and T₃ (9 kg) in a 15 kg capacity tray with three replications. After production, the proximate composition were also measured of fly larvae. Physico-chemical properties such as, color, odor, texture, temperature, pH, total solids (TSS+TDS), chemical oxygen demand, dissolved oxygen, alkalinity, available N, available P, and fiber in raw poultry waste were determined and presented. Proximate composition such as, moisture, total N, total P, available N, total Ca, ash and crude fiber were found in significant amount in the poultry waste. It was found that T₃ (1350±68g) produced highest volume of live maggot compared to the other treatments, but T₂ (17.50±1.10%) produced highest percentage volume. The proximate compositions of fly larvae were assessed and found 56.60±0.25% protein value in it, suggesting that fly larvae could be the protein replacer in fish feed. The result of this study revealed cheap protein source in aquaculture production, such as production and rearing of stinging catfish *Heteropneustes fossilis*, and the findings might be helpful for cost reduction in aquaculture operation.

Keywords: *Lucilia sericata*; raw poultry waste; physico-chemical; fly larvae; proximate composition

1. Introduction

Different agro-industries, including sugar mills, fertilizer factories, and poultry farms, discharge a significant amount of waste and effluent into the waterways and other terrestrial areas, and managing these wastes is a constant concern for the government and other stakeholders (Ayilara *et al.*, 2020; Modak *et al.*, 2019; Reza and Islam, 2019; Samad *et al.*, 2011; Alam and Hossain, 2009). The wastes released from poultry farms may be used

to recycle nutrients through the growth of fly larvae, microalgae, bacteria, and fungi (Gold *et al.*, 2020; Markou *et al.*, 2018; Glatz *et al.*, 2011). High levels of organic nutrients, chemical and biological oxygen demands (COD and BOD), total dissolved solids (TDS), total suspended solids (TSS), Nitrate-N, Ammonia-N, Phosphorus-P, and inorganic nutrients are all present in these wastes (Izzah *et al.*, 2020; Kwon *et al.*, 2020; Yaseen and Scholz, 2019; Abdel-Raouf *et al.*, 2012; Habib *et al.*, 2005). These organic and inorganic nutrients in waste contribute to the growth of microalgae and the biosynthesis of significant amounts of protein, lipids, carbohydrates, and ash (Su *et al.*, 2022; Melo *et al.*, 2018). Chicken manure can encourage the growth and synthesis of additional protein, lipids, and carbohydrates by bacteria, fungus, microalgae, and fly larvae (Hasnol *et al.*, 2020; Cammack and Tomberlin, 2017; Islam *et al.*, 2018). Fly larvae, especially flies (*Lucilia sericata*), can use these nutrients as a cheap alternative (Zhang *et al.*, 2021; Mazza *et al.*, 2020; Parry *et al.*, 2020; Firoozfar *et al.*, 2011).

For the process of raising larvae, especially fly larvae, raw chicken manure includes several essential nutrients, for example, nitrogen, phosphorus, calcium (Bortolini *et al.*, 2020; Lalander *et al.*, 2019; Moon *et al.*, 2001). These nutrients that are not utilized can be recycled, which produces additional support for the growth of other species and lowers their production costs (Manogaran *et al.*, 2022; Szogi *et al.*, 2015). The fly (*L. sericata*) maggot was considered one of the important animal that can be grown in the chicken manure medium (Ali Khan *et al.*, 2012; Hwangbo *et al.*, 2009).

Studies have shown that maggot meal may be a very effective replacement for fish meal, which serves as an excellent source of protein for making fish feed for commercial or small-scale aquaculture (Jahan *et al.*, 2020; Medard *et al.*, 2018; Djissou *et al.*, 2016; Aniebo *et al.*, 2009). Different animal and fish species were used in experiments to determine the impact of using maggot meal instead of other types of protein (Xu *et al.*, 2022; Khan *et al.*, 2016; Makinde and John, 2015; Aniebo *et al.*, 2009). In most cases, maggot meal considered as cheapest and effective nutrient for animal production, including catfish *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Satter *et al.*, 2022; Evangelista *et al.*, 2005).

The nutritional content analysis of processed poultry waste such as, dried, hydrolyzed, and urea-molasses treated were conducted previously (Adli *et al.*, 2018; McNab *et al.*, 1974; Wehunt *et al.*, 1960), however we did not find any study that determined the nutritional, physical and chemical content of raw poultry manure. Therefore, this current study was conducted to determine the nutritional, physical and chemical contents of raw poultry manure for producing and rearing catfish *Heteropneustes fossilis*; additionally the maggot production was also compared in different amount of poultry waste. This study will help to understand the nutritional availability of poultry waste and the production capacity of maggot in different amount of poultry waste.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study area and periods

The experiments were conducted in the wet laboratory, Department of Aquaculture, Suvro poultry farm, Sutiakhali, Mymensingh, and laboratory of the Department of Animal Nutrition, Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh from January 2016 to May 2016 (Figure 1).

2.2. Collection and preparation of poultry waste

The poultry waste was collected from Suvro poultry farm, Sutiakhali, Mymensingh. The poultry farm used to grow and produce fly larvae (maggot) near the farm. Some raw waste was sun-dried grinded, and packed in polythene bag to keep in the laboratory for aerobic digestion and chemical analyses.

2.3. Determination of physico-chemical properties of poultry waste (PW)

Physico-chemical properties of digested PW were analyzed in the laboratories of Live Food Culture, Nutrition and Water Quality of the Faculty of Fisheries, BAU, Mymensingh. The color, odor and texture were evaluated by the human sensory organ. The temperature, the pH and dissolved oxygen (DO) of the digested PW were measured by Celsius thermometer, pH meter (Model HI 98129, HANNA) and digital oxygen meter (Model Nutron DO-5509), respectively using methods described by Islam *et al.* (2016). The chemical oxygen demand was evaluated following the protocols of Hills (1982) and Bortolini *et al.* (2020). The total suspended solid (TSS) and total dissolved solid (TDS) of poultry waste were measured by the procedure of Whitehead (1976) and Larney *et al.* (2014). The alkalinity, total phosphorus (P%) and total nitrogen (N%) of digested PW were measured using APHA (2005) and Das *et al.* (2021) protocols. The crude fiber content of digested PW was determined using the protocols of AOAC (2016).

Figure 1. Poultry waste was collected from Sutiakhali, and lab analysis were conducted in Bangladesh Agricultural University.

2.4. Production and chemical analysis of fly (*Lucilia sericata*) larvae

The fly (*L. sericata*) usually lays eggs on raw poultry waste (PW) and their larvae grow. The flies were allowed to lay eggs in one day old PW in trays of 10 kg capacity (Figure 2A) just nearby a poultry farm situated at Sutiakhali. The fly larvae (maggot) were hatched out at the morning of 2nd day and became big in size ready for collection at the end of 3rd day (Figure 2B). Fly larvae maggot (*L. sericata*) were grown in three different amount of poultry waste namely, T₁ (3 kg), T₂ (6 kg) and T₃ (9 kg) in a 15 kg capacity tray in triplicates under shade (Figure 2A).

Figure 2. production process of fly; A. trays containing raw poultry waste for production of fly (*L. sericata*) larvae (maggot), B. maggot grown in trays on poultry waste on 3rd day, C. oven dried maggot on tray, D. oven dried maggot on tray.

These larvae were collected on 4th day morning. First, the grown larvae in PW were taken on mosquito net, placed in pond water and allowed to washout all the dirt materials from inside the net. Then the net containing the remaining materials was taken out from water and the solid materials were carefully removed. The larvae were picked up using spoon and forceps and kept in plastic bottles. The bottles containing larvae were carried to the laboratory and cleaned using tap water. Some other portion of larvae (maggot) was dried in oven at 50°C overnight (Figure 2 C,D) and the dried maggot was ground, sieved, powder of larvae was packed in polythene bags and kept in deep freeze for future use as ingredient of feed and chemical analysis.

2.5. Determination of proximate composition of poultry waste and larvae

Proximate composition such as moisture, crude protein, crude lipids, ash and nitrogen free extract (NFE) of poultry waste, and fly larvae were analyzed according to standard procedures given by AOAC (2005), Bhuiyan et al. (2018), Nayeem *et al.* (2019) and Khatun *et al.* (2018).

2.6. Data analysis

Three replications were maintained for collecting all the parameters. The collected data were analyzed for mean and standard error (SE) using SAS 9.4 (SAS Institute, 2014). The map was prepared using QGIS Version 3.26.3 (QGIS Development Team, 2019).

3. Results

3.1. Physico-chemical characteristics of raw poultry waste

The color of the poultry waste (PW) was grey with bad smell (odor); while the texture was found almost semi-solid. The temperature of PW ranged between 28.30 and 29.50°C, while the pH values of PW varied between 8.10 and 8.25. The presence of total solid in digested PW (total suspended solids and total dissolved solids) found to be in ranged between 8854 and 8864 mg/L. The dissolved oxygen (DO) of digested PW was ranged between 0 and 0.12 mg/L; while the Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) demand was ranged from 13120 to 13215 mg/L. The alkalinity of digested PW was found 530 to 540 mg/L; while the available N and P was found ranged between 2.60 to 2.70 mg/L and 6.80 to 7.90 mg/L. The Crude fiber was found to be varied from 8.90 to 10.30% in the digested PW (Table 1).

Table 1. Physico-chemical characteristics of raw poultry waste just after collection.

Characteristics of raw poultry waste	Findings
Color	Grayish
Odor	Bad smell
Texture	Semi-solid
Temperature	28.30-29.50°C
pH	8.10-8.50
Total solids (TSS + TDS)	88540-88640 mg/L
Chemical oxygen demand	131200-132150 mg/L
Dissolved oxygen	0-0.12 mg/L
Alkalinity	530-540 mg/L
Available N	2.60-2.70 mg/L
Available P	6.80-7.90 mg/L
Fibre	8.90-10.30%

3.2. Proximate composition of poultry waste on dry weight basis

Moisture was measured from semi-solid wet poultry waste ranged between 16.73 to 17.73% (17.23±0.50%). Total N of poultry waste was varied from 3.94 to 4.50 % (4.30±0.15%). Total P was found to be ranged from 6.80 to 7.90 mg/L. Available N was found to vary from 2.12 to 2.50% (2.25±0.12%). Total Ca of poultry waste was varied from 14.95 to 15.75% (15.45±0.34%). It was found that ash content of poultry waste was very high and ranged from 22.95 to 26.65% (24.55±0.62%). Crude fiber in poultry waste was not high in amount but ranged from 8.90 to 10.30% (9.60 ± 0.24%) (Table 2).

Table 2. Chemical composition (%) of poultry waste on dry basis.

Moisture	Total N	Total P	Available N	Total Ca	Ash	Crude Fiber
17.23±0.50	4.30±0.15	5.03±0.18	2.25±0.12	15.45±0.34	24.55±0.62	9.60±0.24

3.3. Production and chemical analysis of fly larvae in poultry waste

It was found the T₃ produced highest amount of live maggot (1350±68 g) followed by T₂ (1050±40 g) and T₁ (480±20 g) (Table 3). The percent production estimation suggested that, T₂ (17.50±1.10 %) produced highest percent of live maggot from poultry waste followed by T₁ (16.00±1.15 %) and T₃ (15.00±0.95 %). The higher dry weight of maggot was found in T₃ (138.70±7.40), followed by T₂ (109.20±6.70) and T₁ (49.50±3.55).

Table 3. Production of fly larvae (maggot) in different amount of poultry waste.

Treatment	Production of live maggot (g)	Percentage of production	Dry weight (g)
T ₁	480±20	16.00±1.15	49.50±3.55
T ₂	1050±40	17.50±1.10	109.20±6.70
T ₃	1350±68	15.00±0.95	138.70±7.40

It was recorded that moisture content of maggot was 10.88±0.10%, where crude protein was 56.60±0.25%, crude lipids was 15.80±0.10%, ash content was 15.40±0.07% and NFE (nitrogen free extract) was 1.22±0.02% (Table 4).

Table 4. Average proximate composition (%) of fly (*L. sericata*) larvae (Maggot) grown in different trays.

Name of ingredient	Moisture	Crude protein	Crude lipids	Ash	NFE*
Maggot	10.88±0.10	56.60±0.25	15.80±0.10	15.40±0.07	1.22±0.02

*NFE (Nitrogen free extract) = 100 – (crude protein + crude lipids + ash)

4. Discussion

Production of fly (*L. sericata*) maggot using raw and digested poultry waste, the use of live maggot as protein source and maggot meal as the fish meal replacer in the production of the stinging catfish, *Heteropneustes fossilis* were the main key goal of this research. However, the physical and chemical composition of raw poultry waste was described by several researches while the color of the waste were grayish to black according to their states and the odors generated were due to the presence of volatile organic compounds (VOCs), ammonia (NH₃), hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), greenhouse gases, and particulate matter (Kopeck *et al.*, 2018; Kalus *et al.*, 2017; Passos *et al.*, 2014; Yetilmezsoy and Sakar, 2008). The semi-solid texture of raw poultry waste comprised a pH value of above 7.5, referring the alkaline condition of the material (Pizarro *et al.*, 2019; Finch *et al.*, 2014). The total suspended solid of poultry waste was reported 5,020 ± 380 mg/L in the research of Yetilmezsoy and Sakar (2008), however the present study suggested the range can be varied from 8854-8864 mg/L due to the mixture of the other organic particles with the raw poultry waste. The chemical oxygen demand of the digested poultry waste found higher due to high organic material content, resulting the low dissolved oxygen (DO) and high biologically active organics (Yetilmezsoy and Sakar, 2008; Whitehead, 1976). The total alkalinity of the digested poultry waste found to be higher (530-540 mg/L), due to high mineral contents especially the mollusk shells fed during the broiler production system; while studies also found moderate alkalinity of 170±30 mg/L in the poultry waste (Wasserfurth *et al.*, 2019; Rehman *et al.*, 2012). The available nitrogen content of the digested poultry waste was found to be 2.60-2.70 mg/L, while the raw form might have slightly higher nitrogen content than the digested form (Elasri and El amin Afilal, 2016). The presence of phosphorus in the waste was found 6.80-7.90 mg/L, while phosphorus in the mineral form of poultry waste can be considered one of the great organic source (Waldrip *et al.*, 2011; Sarker *et al.*, 2009).

The production of live maggot were ranged between 480 ± 20g and 1350 ± 68g, while the dry weight of the produced maggot ranged between 49.50 ± 3.55g and 138.70 ± 7.40g using 3 and 12kg poultry waste. Different studies suggested to use the cow dung, human waste, fruit waste, spend coffee ground, soybean dregs, etc. and they found different production rate and dry weight (Gougbedji *et al.*, 2021; Permana and Ramadhani Eka Putra, 2018; Banks *et al.*, 2014).

The fly larvae comprised high protein, 56.60±0.25%, lipids 15.80±0.10% and ash content 15.40±0.07%, referring the potentiality of the maggot placing as feed material, especially as the protein source for human or

cultured animal (Odesanya *et al.*, 2011). However, the price of the protein found always high in the market and considered one of the greatest challenges for reducing the price of the aquaculture final product (Hua *et al.*, 2019; Fry *et al.*, 2018; Dickson *et al.*, 2016; Hyuha *et al.*, 2011). There are many different sources of protein, and most of them require to culture in farm which need to keep high standard and as we were seeking for a cheap and standard protein source, considering fly larvae as the most inexpensive and low maintenance production-able protein source (Tippayadara *et al.*, 2021; Egerton *et al.*, 2020; Chen *et al.*, 2019; Al-Thobaiti *et al.*, 2018).

5. Conclusions

Therefore, it can be said that poultry waste is an ideal environment for the development of fly larvae (maggot). Maggot is a highly suitable food item, one of the main ingredients of feed as well as live or frozen food for fish post-larvae, fry, or fingerlings, according to nutritional analysis and proximate composition (herbivorous, carnivorous and omnivorous fishes). The use of fly larvae in fish feed production might reduce the cost of aquaculture operation.

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Data availability

The data of this current investigation will be available upon valid request by any authority from the corresponding author.

Conflict of interest

None to declare.

Authors' contribution

Abdus Satter: conceptualization, methodology, analysis and manuscript writing; Md. Ahsan Bin Habib: Supervision, conceptualization, methodology, reviewing and editing; Hadi Hamli: reviewing and editing; Abdulla-Al-Asif: data analysis, interpretation, graphical presentation and map preparation, reviewing and editing; Jamil: reviewing and editing. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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